

5 Poems by Jyotirmaya Thakur

Bees

I want so desperately
to be proven wrong
when I watch the bees take
most of the metaphor with them.

Wilds

Consider the verbal dearth
that is always a main ripple
of extinction
when the lexicon of wilds
goes on nixing its descriptions.

Elegy

Who weeps the way a willow does,
silently as wax burned in the land of milk and all the strong words in poems
are but the elegy of an abandoned lover.

Solitary

I live without caution now
that I am older,
and still love the innocent
and foolish child in me.
I looked up from my solitary
suffering
to create a history of life without fear.

A Poet

I confess, I have been a poet
since a hawk circles overhead
as the world turns its one good eye away from peace and embraces war.

Bio:

Jyotirmaya Thakur (retired Principal) is an International acclaimed bilingual author of fifty books and Co - author of many International Anthologies. Multi - genre award winning author of many awards from literary and humanitarian organisations. A columnist , researcher, reviewer, translator, spiritual ,social and environmental activist . She serves on various prestigious Committees as International Ambassador and honorary Advisor in many literary and humanitarian organisations.

Her work has been published in many anthologies, magazines internationally and translated in many languages. She is compared to Wordsworth for her Nature poems and with John Keats for sensuousness. Her love poems are divine like the Sufi. Her poetry opens for the reader a new spiritual perspective about the world. She has received many international awards and is yearly invited to the most prestigious international poetry conferences.